

Cultural Dimensions as Determinants of Trust on E-Commerce by SMMEs in Limpopo Province of South Africa

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Since the COVID-19 lockdown, businesses have realised the effectiveness of e-commerce in their value chains. However, the adoption of e-commerce by SMEs in developing countries has remained lagging. This study has reviewed the literature to establish factors influencing e-commerce adoption. Underpinned by the positivist paradigm, the study adopted a quantitative approach. The cultural factor was identified as a key factor influencing e-commerce adoption in developing countries. A survey was carried out to establish the influence of culture on the adoption of e-commerce by SMEs in Limpopo province. A questionnaire was used to collect data from randomly sampled 400 SMMEs from three districts in the Limpopo province of South Africa. The software SPSS was used to analyse data. Regression analysis was applied to test the influence of culture on trust in e-commerce. Demographic factors such as age, level of education, gender, and knowledge of computers were used as control variables. The study findings proved that cultural dimensions influence trust in e-commerce. The demographics proved to have no significant influence on trust in e-commerce. This study contributes to the theory of technology adoption. The study also contributes to formulating government policy that promotes e-commerce as an agent for sustainable development.

Keywords: e-commerce, cultural dimensions, adoption, SMEs, developing countries

Advances in technology continue to revolutionise the ways of doing business worldwide. Big businesses in developed countries now depend on digitalisation for most of the components of their value chains. E-commerce has facilitated improved efficiency in big business across the world (Raidi et al., 2021). The contribution of e-commerce to sustainable development cannot be underestimated (Kwilinski, 2023).

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) continue to be viewed as contributors to the economies of developing countries (Pulka & Gawuna, 2022). SMEs in developing countries have not established themselves with e-commerce business models. E-commerce has the potential to facilitate market expansion, improve communication, reduce administrative costs and access to global markets, enhance global supply chains, promote value chain integration, and reduce operational expenses (Raidi et al., 2021).

Many studies have assessed the various factors influencing technology adoption in Developing Countries. Many scholarly articles identify social influence as one of the critical influences on behavioural intention to adopt technology within SMEs (VanDerSchaaf, 2021). Cultural dimensions can be classified as one of the social factors influencing technology adoption.

Problem Statement

The COVID-19 lockdown saw many businesses adopting e-

commerce as an effective alternative to doing business under prevailing conditions (Galhotra & Dewan, 2020). Ever since, the benefits of e-commerce to business continue to increase with every advancement in technology (Sulova, 2023). New technologies are adding to the existing benefits of using e-commerce in businesses, resulting in further improvement in efficiency. General trust in e-commerce by consumers in developed countries also keeps increasing, and some now entirely depend on e-commerce for basic shopping (Jain et al., 2021). Meanwhile, the role of trust in influencing consumer decisions on e-commerce has seen big brands find it easy to adopt e-commerce. Due to existing trust, consumers will not hesitate to do business with established brands.

Whilst SMEs in developing countries have suffered from business loss during the Covid-19 lockdown period, logically, the post-COVID era should realise their aggressive efforts to adopt e-commerce in anticipation of similar future circumstances and in appreciation of the efficiency that comes with e-commerce (Cordes & Marinova, 2023). Considering the subjective nature of social influence, few studies have explored the influence of cultural dimensions in different contexts on adopting e-commerce. Given the persistent lag in the adoption of e-commerce by SMEs in developing countries like South Africa, the gap remains in focusing more on contextual social factors likely influencing adoption (Chauhan, 2023). The strides in reducing the digital divide over the recent years (Cariolle, 2021) do not match the levels of e-commerce adoption by SMEs in developing South Africa. There is a need for further research to use empirical evidence to prove the impact of social influence on adopting e-commerce. The effect of culture on technology acceptance models has not been sufficiently studied (Jan, Alshare, & Lane, 2024).

Aim of the Study

This study aimed to investigate the impact of culture on SMEs' trust in e-commerce in the Limpopo province of South Africa.

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Objectives of the Study

- To establish the relevance of e-commerce in SME businesses in the Limpopo Province of South Africa.
- To identify cultural dimensions relevant to the SMEs in Limpopo.
- To evaluate the influence of culture on trust in e-commerce for SMEs in the Limpopo province of South Africa.
- To establish the influence of demographic variables on trust in e-commerce in the Limpopo province of South Africa

Research Questions

- What relevance does e-commerce have in SMEs in the Limpopo Province of South Africa?
- What cultural dimensions are relevant to the SMEs in Limpopo?
- What is the influence of cultural dimensions on trust in e-commerce for SMEs in the Limpopo province of South Africa?
- How do demographic factors influence SMEs' trust in e-commerce in the Limpopo province of South Africa?

Review of Literature

This section defines e-commerce and then discusses the relevance of e-commerce in SMEs as given in the literature. Factors that influence the adoption of e-commerce are also explored. This section also reviews theories relating to technology adoption and how they align with the study's objectives. With big businesses leveraging e-commerce to improve their businesses, there is a need to explore the opportunities for SMEs in developing countries. The contribution of e-commerce to sustainable development cannot be underestimated (Kwilinski, 2023).

E-commerce is a business model that lets firms and individuals buy and sell products and services over the Internet (Sharma, 2020; Riadi et al., 2022). Madzvamuse (2024) and Mishra listed seven e-commerce features that improve business efficiency (2020). These features are ubiquity, global reach, interactivity, universal standards, richness, information density and personalisation. According to (Jain, 2021), E-commerce facilitates market expansion beyond traditional boundaries. Businesses can market products and do business with consumers in all regions globally. The market size for e-commerce businesses matches the world's online population, which is estimated to be above two billion (Madzvamuse, 2024; Naseri, 2021) and involves millions of businesses worldwide. For consumers, e-commerce improves market participation and reduces transaction costs (Raidi et al., 2021).

Through e-commerce, communication in business improves. The use of technology to communicate reduces costs for marketing and product support. Internet technologies have given rise to communication applications that support the sharing of high-quality information across businesses. Information in multimedia formats, including video, sound, text, and graphics. Multimedia facilitates quality marketing messages and the exchange of consuming experiences. E-commerce greatly improves access to information (Taher, 2021). Opportunities for global reach include a global product market, a global supply chain, multiple language support, and franchising (Madzvamuse, 2024; Guercini, 2015).

E-commerce as a technology also brings the advantage of the Internet's international technical standards. All nations share the Internet standards worldwide (Madzvamuse, 2024; Spindler, 2020). The Internet Protocol provides a universal standard for sharing data. Considering the importance of data in all business decisions,

businesses use data mining technologies to obtain essential data. These e-commerce features and the ever-advancing technology have improved business efficiency and profitability. So much research has explored the factors influencing e-commerce, but it remains a concern that SMEs from developing countries like South Africa have not adequately adopted e-commerce (Urban, 202; Jere, 2020).

E-commerce in SMEs

The aim of the October 2016 African Union Commission (AUC) SMEs Strategy and Master Plan review (2017-2021) was to improve the continental business environment by fostering more businesses through formalisation and the supported growth of informal enterprises. The SMEs Strategy Master Plan demonstrates efforts by developing African countries to promote sustainable development by supporting SMEs (Madzvamuse, 2024; AU Directorate of Communication, 2016). As evidenced by this strategy and master plan, SMEs play an important role in promoting the goals of sustainable development (Kwilinski, 2023; Darrold, 2023).

One of the significant challenges to SMEs in developing countries is the reluctance to change (Hendricks, 2024; Ndayizigamiye, 2019; Rawash, 2021). The COVID-19 lockdown restricted movement to limit direct physical human contact, which posed an inherent risk of covid virus infection. The digital economy became an essential factor in alleviating the economic challenges posed by the lockdown. The lockdown dramatically enhanced the digital economy in developing countries, resulting in increased demand for e-commerce services (Hendricks, 2024). With this background, one would anticipate the desire of SMEs in developing countries to adopt e-commerce. What is apparent within SMEs in South Africa is a reluctance to embrace e-commerce (Gallant, 2024).

According to Alkhunaizan (2022), the demand for e-commerce products and services rose significantly during the COVID-19 lockdown. Non-regular e-commerce services, such as food deliveries, balanced the negative growth of the hard-hit transportation and travel sectors during the lockdown. Despite the potential of e-commerce for SMEs to expand their businesses into new markets, the lack of knowledge of IT applications needed to make e-commerce more appealing and relevant to their businesses remains a reality (Madzvamuse, 2024). SME enterprises' sizes and relatively limited budgets further impact their development (Madzvamuse, 2024; Kumar, 2021; Ndayizigamiye, 2019). As the digital divide narrows in developing countries, research has focused on the other barriers to technology adoption, and culture has been featured (Ahluwalia, 2021). The influence of culture on SMEs' business operations in South Africa is very significant (Ayandibu, 2023).

Cultural Dimensions and SMEs

Researchers have adopted Hofstede's theory of cultural differences in exploring cultural influence in societies (Minkov, 2022; Tejay, 2017). Hofstede's theory identified six dimensions of culture. These dimensions are Collectivism versus Individualism (IDV), Power Distance Index (PDI), Femininity versus Masculinity (MAS), Short Term Normative versus Long Term Orientation (LTO), Uncertainty Avoidance, and Restraint versus Indulgence (Rabayah, 2021; Tejay, 2017; Hofstede, 2010). Previous studies explain how cultural background influences behavioural intentions (Nagy, 2022). As such, it is logical to conclude that the cultural backgrounds of individuals working in SMEs could have some influence on their behaviour at work (Huang, 2022).

The power distance index (PDI) dimension is a value that describes societies that differentiate people based on the degree to which inequalities are acceptable, either as unavoidable or as functional within the society (Madzvamuse, 2023; Daniels, 2014). This cultural dimension manifests in SMEs in South Africa. Considering SMEs in the transport sector, influential individuals are known to control the industry. Players in the industry have accepted the inequalities in power (Geldenhuys, 2022) demonstrating a high-power distance index within the industry. Some cultures have a lower PDI than others (Tejay, 2017) and power relations are more democratic; therefore, subordinates can contribute to decisions.

For Collectivism versus individualism, people are likely to define themselves as aspects of groups, prioritise goals and communal relationships, and members are self-effacing. On the contrary, individualistic societies gratify personal achievements (Xiao, 2021; Triandis, 2002). Collectivist cultures shape many workers in SMEs in South Africa. Some of the SMEs include sectors such as event planning, garment manufacturing and the food industry. Workers in these industries prioritise given goals as shaped by their cultures.

Masculinity versus femininity refers to the difference in gender and the values associated with each by tradition. Highly masculine societies have values of materialism, competitiveness, ambition, power, and assertiveness, while feminine cultures value love and caring for the weak, better living standards, collaboration, and humility (Tejay, 2017). In a society with a high MAS index, males assume more assertive roles, and there is a division in roles by gender, while a low MAS index results in a gender balance in teams. Many SME enterprises in South Africa are gender specific.

The uncertainty avoidance index (UAI) refers to society's acceptance of uncertainty. The UAI corresponds to the desire to minimise societal anxiety and uncertainty, as reflected through the index (Xu & Cheng, 2021; Hofstede, 2010). Xu and Chen (2021) established that cultures with high levels of uncertainty avoidance are likely not to trust e-commerce. Highly uncertain avoidance emanates from the desire to avoid risk. Considering specific SMEs in South Africa, the food industry prioritises popular dishes within specific traditions. Event organisers stick with procedures associated with the culture of the hosting families. Garment manufacturers prefer to specialise in garment designs that certain cultures prefer. Low uncertainty avoidance cultures are comfortable with unstructured situations or changes and, as such, might easily gain trust in e-commerce.

Societies with long-term orientation (LTO) are preoccupied with the future and foster realistic principles oriented toward persistence, rewards, and opportunities for adaptation. On the contrary, short-term-oriented societies are concerned with sticking to traditions and truthfulness, achieving immediate results, self-preservation, fulfilling social obligations, and reciprocating (Madzvamuse, 2024; Tejay, 2017; Hofstede et al., 2010). Regarding technology adoption, the orientation of these opposing cultures varies, revealing that each has pros and cons when adopting technology and e-commerce. LTO societies tend to consider a well-calculated approach to adoption that factors into the possible future benefits. A cautious approach might also result in procrastination. The STO cultures will make quick decisions on adopting technologies, which can be good if favourable outcomes exist (Madzvamuse, 2024).

With Restraint versus Indulgence, societies with indulgence believe in satisfying humans' basic natural desires and having fun (Tejay, 2017) while high-restraint societies restrict gratification of needs through strict social values. There is always a calculated

approach to any behaviour weighed against the social values of the restrained society (Minkov, 2022).

Hallikainen and Laukkanen (2018) evaluated the relationship between national cultural dimensions and trust. This study tested the impact of each cultural dimension on trust in general; since a society's willingness to use e-commerce depends on its trust in the technology, the study tested five hypotheses to evaluate the causal effect of nations. This study adopted the conclusion from Hallikainen that the nation's cultural dimension influences trust values. The study proposed that the cultural dimension of a society has an impact on its trust in e-commerce.

Theoretical Framework

Using theory in research helps to understand a phenomenon and gain deeper insights into practice (Calder, 2023). Many theories relate to the adoption of technologies. This study found the diffusion of innovation DOI and the UTAUT theories relevant to the phenomenon under study.

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI)

The diffusion of innovation refers to the process that occurs when people adopt a new idea. With the creation of innovation being a continuous process, Acikgoz (2023) alluded that accepting any invention is subject to the individual's attitude towards the innovation. Social science studies recognise cultural dimensions' role in influencing individuals' attitudes (Jeong, 2021). This study will test the DOI theory by evaluating the influence of Cultural dimensions on trust in e-commerce. Trust is a positive attitude that may result in adoption.

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

The UTAUT theory identifies four independent variables influencing the information system user's behavioural intention: expected effort, performance expectation, social impact, and facilitating conditions (Lee & Kim, 2022). According to Lee, performance expectancy relates to expected benefits, effort expectancy relates to the ease of use for the technology, social influence relates to how others in the society influence the use, and facilitating conditions include the available resources allowing the use of the technology. Considering Cultural dimensions to be a social aspect, this study tests the social impact variable of the theory.

Cultural Dimensions and Trust in e-commerce

Jan (2024) alluded that users' perception of technology adoption is possibly influenced by the individual differences and culture of the organisation, national culture, or even by the characteristics of the technology itself (Jan, 2024). Previous research has concluded that the level of Trust influences technology adoption (Choudhury & Shamszare, 2023). Having adopted the relationship between the concepts of Trust and technology adoption, this study used empirical evidence to confirm the relationship between culture and Trust. Hofstede's cultural dimensions were selected to measure culture using the study's context and literature findings.

Hofstede's theory identified the Power distance index as one of the dimensions of culture. Research has established a relationship between PDI and the adoption of technology (Ciftci, 2021; Khan & Rashid, 2021). High power distance has been concluded to have a negative influence on the adoption of technology.

Bokhari and Myeong (2023) established that Collectivism negatively influences technology adoption compared to individualism. A study by Hamza et al. (2025) confirmed that the long-term orientation cultural dimension exhibited a negative, albeit statistically insignificant, technology adoption appetite. Ayob (2021) alluded that adopting e-commerce is more trusted by societies that exhibit low uncertainty avoidance, high individualism and low masculinity. Motivated by previous studies that have investigated and confirmed the relationship between culture and Trust in technology, this study aimed to contribute by specifically exploring the influence of cultural dimensions on Trust in e-commerce.

Demographics Variables

Besides testing the influence of cultural dimensions on Trust in e-commerce by SMMEs in Limpopo, it was essential to consider control variables likely to affect the study's results. Control variables are factors that researchers include in their work to strengthen findings on causal relationships and rule out alternative explanations for their conclusions (Li, 2021; Becker, 2005; Schmitt, 1991).

Li (2021) emphasised that improperly handling control variables can result in misleading results. The following controlling variables were considered for this research: Age, Gender, Education Level, Internet Experience and District of origin for the SME.

Over the years, due to cultural connotations, women have been identified as hesitant to adopt technology in many societies (Radovic Markovic, 2021). In contrast to the traditional reality, Li (2025) confirmed that the relationship between behavioural intention and use behaviour exhibited greater strength among females than males. In the same study, urban dwellers were confirmed to be most likely to have intentions to adopt technology compared to rural dwellers. Individuals with higher educational backgrounds find Behavioural intention and use behaviour to be stronger relative to those with lower educational backgrounds (Ma, Wang, Li, Wang, & Wang, 2025). Research findings have also established a negative correlation between technology adoption intentions and age (Granić, Andrina, 2022).

Considering the study context and supported by findings from the literature, the study identified Age, Gender, Education Level, Internet Experience and District of origin as suitable control variables. The study tested the influence of these variables on Trust in e-commerce.

Conceptual Model

Guided by the literature review, this study proposed the following hypotheses as illustrated in the model in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Conceptual Model for the Influence of Cultural Dimensions on Trust in e-commerce

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: Cultural Dimensions influence the Trust in e-commerce by SMMEs in Limpopo Province
- *H2*: Age has an insignificant influence on Trust in e-commerce by SMEs in Limpopo province.
- *H3*: Gender has an insignificant influence on Trust in e-commerce by SMEs in Limpopo province.
- *H4*: Level of education has an insignificant influence on Trust in e-commerce by SMEs in Limpopo province.
- *H5*: Knowledge of the Internet has an insignificant influence on Trust in e-commerce by SMEs in Limpopo province.
- *H6*: The district of origin has an insignificant influence on Trust in e-commerce by SMEs in Limpopo province.

Method

The study took a Positivist approach, establishing explanatory associations or causal relationships through quantitative approaches using empirical data and a large sample size (Park, 2020). Ontologically, positivism assumes objectivity of reality, which is independent from the researcher (Creswell, 2018). Epistemologically, Positivists believe that knowledge is solely based on observable facts independent of any individual's mind. A survey was conducted on SMMEs from three districts in the Limpopo province of South Africa. A sample of 500 SMEs was used, and data were collected using a questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of two parts, with the first section capturing the respondent's demographic information, such as age, level of education, gender, internet experience and the district of origin for the SME. The second part consisted of Likert scale questions (scale of 1= *strongly disagree* to 5 =*strongly agree*) to depict the SMMEs owners' perceptions of the cultural dimension in their business environment. The dependent variable in this study was Trust in e-commerce. The collected data were analysed using SPSS software.

Results

The study deployed approximately 550 questionnaires through trained research assistants who administered the questionnaires. All possible recipients were recorded. A total of 463 responses were received, and of these, 421 responses were complete and usable for quantitative data analysis. The response rate was above 50 % and is very good for the study (Dillman, 2020).

Respondent Profiles

Profiles of respondents were classified using five categories, which are Gender, age, education level, Internet experience, and Business Sector. The researchers did not use a predefined list in the business sector to allow any new categories of SMMEs to emerge. In respect to Gender, there was a slight difference in the composition of respondents, with Males constituting 46.1 % and females 53,9 % (see Table 5.1).

Table 1

Participants' Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	194	46.1
Male	227	53.9

On age, 23% of the respondents were between 18 and 34 years old, 51.8% were between 35 and 54 years old, and 25,2 % were above 55 years old. Based on this result, most of the SME owners are middle-aged (see Table 2).

Table 2*Respondents' Age*

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 - 34 years	97	23.0
35 - 54 years	218	51.8
55 years and above	106	25.2

The respondents with a level of education below high school were the majority, 37.54%. Respondents with a High School constituted 29,5 %, those with a bachelor's degree 21,4%, and 11,6% had a postgraduate qualification (see Table 3).

Table 3*Respondents' Level of Education*

Level of Education	Frequency	Percent
Below High School	158	37.5
High School	124	29.5
Bachelor's Degree	90	21.4
Postgraduate	49	11.6

On knowledge about the internet, 70,2 % of the respondents claimed to be highly knowledgeable, 19,2% slightly, and 10,6 % were not knowledgeable (see Table 5.4).

Table 4*Respondents' Knowledge of the Use of the Internet*

Internet Knowledge	Frequency	Percent
Not at all	42	10.6
Highly knowledgeable	298	70.2
Slightly knowledgeable	81	19,2

The SMMEs from three districts of Limpopo, namely Vhembe, Mopani and Sekhukhune, were considered for this Survey. The distribution of respondents per district was 54,6 % for Vhembe, 33,3 % for Mopani and 12,1 % for Sekhukhune (see Table 5).

Table 5*Respondents' Province*

Province	Frequency	Percent
Vhembe	230	54.6
Mopani	140	33.3
Sekhukhune	51	12.1

A variety of SME categories were represented among the respondents. Common sectors were the food industry (including fruit and vegetable vending), the transport industry, Beauty therapy, event management, and garment manufacturing.

Table 6 describes the composition of responses by participants to survey questions contributing to the Cultural Dimensions and Trust in e-commerce constructs.

Table 6*Constructs for Cultural Dimensions (CD) and Trust on E-Commerce (ET)*

Indices	Description	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
CD1	Powerful individuals control our business sector and how the business operates	30,5	23,6	16,5	14,2	15,2
CD2	Division of roles based on gender is essential in my business sector.	8,2	8,4	20,6	31,6	31,2
CD3	We stick to our traditional products and services, which are preferred by our customers	16,6	24,4	35,5	17,2	6,3
CD4	Improvements to our services are influenced by long-term benefits to our society	8,2	9,5	23,2	31,0	28,1
CD5	Our products and services aim to preserve our cultural values rather than targeting to impress individual tests.	6,2	11,6	30,3	37,7	14,2
ET1	The use of e-commerce in my business will have long-term benefits	6,1	10,3	22,2	36,6	24,8
ET2	Use of e-commerce (doing business on the internet), will see my business penetrate new markets	3,1	10,4	25,1	34,2	27,2
ET3	E-commerce (doing business on the internet) will improve access to information in my business sector.	4,2	11,3	15,5	46,3	22,7
ET4	E-commerce will allow businesses in my sector, to do business across all levels	5,9	22,4	17,4	30,2	24,1

Analysis of the Technological Preparedness Factor Items

The Cultural dimension factor scale was made up of five items. A Cronbach's alpha of 0.846 was obtained on the Technological Preparedness factors. The reliability coefficient is acceptable (Pallant, 2020). The Corrected-Item total correlation column in Table 7 shows that all the item-total correlations are above the cut-off level. No poor items were identified; hence, all items were retained.

Table 7*Reliability Statistics for Cultural Dimension Construct*

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
0,846	0,847	5

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
CD1	13,71	9,418	0,599	0,421	0,823
CD2	13,08	9,517	0,572	0,463	0,714
CD3	13,87	11,611	0,713	0,398	0,791
CD4	13,01	10,571	0,717	0,564	0,854
CD5	13,09	10,597	0,679	0,537	0,851

Multiple Regression Analysis

This study identified a set of control variables (age, gender, internet experience, education level, & District of origin). Determining the significance of the relationship between these control variables and the dependent variable is essential. Thus, the first part was the analysis of the regression of the controller variables on the dependent variable. The second part tested the regression of the demographics together with the independent variable (Cultural

Dimensions) on the dependent variable.

Table 8 summarises the regression analysis results, showing the two models separately. Model 1 shows the regression analysis results for age, gender, education level, Internet experience, and District (control variables) on the Trust in E-commerce (dependent variable). Model 2 demonstrates the combined model's effect, which includes the controllers and the independent variable Cultural Dimensions (CD) on Trust in E-Commerce (ET) when applying the regression analysis.

Table 8

Summary for the Regression Analysis Test

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.139 ^a	0,021	0,012	0,73635	
2	.792 ^b	0,610	0,603	0,45030	

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5,722	5	1,153	2,212	.052 ^b
	Residual	267,892	361	0,531		
	Total	273,614	366			
2	Regression	162,471	9	17,953	84,694	.000 ^c
	Residual	102,221	476	0,212		
	Total	254,703	488			

The results of the regression analysis show that model 1 is not significant ($p > 0.001$), while model 2 is significant ($p < .001$). The R² suggests that the independent variable (Cultural Dimensions) can explain 60% (R Square multiplied by 100) of the variance determining Trust in e-commerce. The test controlled the effects of education level, age, Internet experience, gender, and district. The VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) values vary between 1.293 and 2,898, indicating the absence of multicollinearity. The study found all the predictors (independent variables) in the model significant. According to the data sample, the beta weight in Cultural

Dimensions ($\beta = 0.163$).

For the results from the controllers, though model 1 is insignificant ($p > 0.001$), gender, age, and Internet knowledge significantly influence Trust in e-commerce. According to the results, males have more Trust in e-commerce. Age has an inverse influence on Trust in e-commerce, while the level of education and internet knowledge directly influence Trust in e-commerce. The influence of the level of education was meagre for this sample. Therefore, the results of the regression analysis support the hypotheses (See Table 9).

Table 9

Regression Test Results Implications on Hypotheses

Relationship	Hypothesis	β	Sig	Outcome
Cultural Dimensions influence Trust in e-commerce.	H1	0.163	.000 ^c	Supported and significant
Gender, Age, Level of education, Internet experience and District influence trust on e-commerce.	H2 - H5	<0.1	.052 ^b	Not significant

Discussion

Based on empirical evidence, this study confirms the causal relationship between cultural dimensions and Trust in e-commerce. The study applied Regression analysis to test the hypotheses:

Cultural Dimensions Influence Trust in E-commerce

Demographic variables (Gender, age, level of education, knowledge of the internet and district of SME origin) have an insignificant influence on Trust in e-commerce in Limpopo province of South Africa.

Cultural dimensions were found to influence Trust in e-commerce for SMEs significantly was found to be significant. The findings align with previous studies that have confirmed the influence of cultural dimensions on adopting technology (Jan, 2024; Bokhari & Myeong, 2023; Ciftci, 2021; Ayob, 2021; Khan & Rashid, 2021).

Previous studies have also tested the influence of demographics such as gender, age, level of education, knowledge of the internet and place of origin on adoption. Although the combined influence of the demographics on Trust in e-commerce was found insignificant ($p > 0.01$), some demographics, such as age, knowledge of the internet and level of education, had little influence on Trust in e-commerce. This confirmed the findings of some previous studies (Ma, Wang, Li, Wang, & Wang, 2025; Granić, 2022). Some studies have also confirmed the influence of gender on the adoption of technology, which was found to be insignificant by this study.

Conclusion

This study contributes to knowledge by testing adoption theories using empirical data. Understanding the influence of cultural dimensions on trust in e-commerce can contribute to policy. In drafting policies that promote the use of technology by SMEs to improve business efficiency, government departments may consider putting measures that eliminate cultural polarisation in SMEs. Although the study only considered three districts in Limpopo, the selected districts provided the expected level of cultural diversity, thereby contributing to the credibility of the findings. Further studies can be carried out to establish the influence of specific cultural dimensions on identified types of SMEs in South Africa.

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